

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Authoring Cell Type Annotation Crosswalks

Linking cell type annotations from different teams, tools, and assay types to cell types in the Cell Ontology

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Introduction

Cell type annotation represents one of the most critical and challenging steps in single-cell and spatial omics data analysis. The field has evolved rapidly with the development of numerous computational methods, each addressing different aspects of the annotation process and revealing significant diversity in how bioinformatics groups approach this fundamental task (Li et al. 2025). To add complexity, the nomenclature that each group uses for cell types is not standardized, often using abbreviations or vague terminology at different levels of specificity. The difference in terminology complicates comparison across datasets and organs, especially when comparing different types of data. To provide harmonized annotations in support of atlas construction, the Cell Ontology (CL) (Diehl et al. 2016) serves as a foundational standardization framework that addresses the fundamental challenge of inconsistent cell type naming and classification across different research groups.

This standard operating procedure (SOP) describes how to create a cell type annotation crosswalk for a new dataset using table templates; how to add appropriate metadata; and how to submit a cell type annotation crosswalk as a Human Reference Atlas (HRA) digital object. It provides guidelines on how to map cell types to ontologies, and how to deal with cell types that are not yet available in CL. The primary audiences for this SOP are cell type annotation (CTann) tool developers and ontology experts that author cell type annotation crosswalk tables. This SOP assumes basic working knowledge of bash, intermediate knowledge of ontologies, and advanced knowledge in cell biology.

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Roles and Responsibilities

The **HRA Technical Lead** is responsible for maintaining the code used to map cell types into CL.

External Reviewers are cell ontologist experts who review relevant portions of the cell type annotation crosswalk tables and suggest improvements or corrections.

Internal Reviewers are experts deeply familiar with the HRA that inspect cell type annotation crosswalks for their completeness and utility in atlas construction and usage.

The **Lead Crosswalk Author** is an expert on cell types curation and linkage to CL. They take responsibility for mapping all cell types from a dataset into CL. The result is one cell type annotation crosswalk table per cell type annotation tool or method.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
HRA Technical Lead	Bruce W. Herr II	bherr@iu.edu
External Reviewers	various	various
Internal Reviewers	Katy Börner Bruce W. Herr II	katy@iu.edu bherr@iu.edu
Lead Crosswalk Author	Aleix Puig Nicole A. Vasilevsky	aleix@ebi.ac.uk nvasilevsky@c-path.org

Procedures

A crosswalk table template is available at [Cell Type Annotation Crosswalk Template](#). The template is also included as an appendix.

Crosswalk table metadata: first 10 rows

Analogous to other HRA digital object tables, the first 10 rows of the crosswalk table are reserved for metadata. Row 1 contains the name of the table, "Cell Type Annotation Crosswalk." Row 2 is intentionally left blank. Rows 3-10 include information about the authors, reviewers, general reference publications, the digital object identifier (DOI) of the table, and the date and version of the table. For details about rows 3-10, see the SOP on authoring crosswalk pathway tables (Weber and Gustilo 2024).

Table columns

Row 11 contains the name of the table columns. There are 7 columns:

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- **Organ_Level:** Describes the anatomical structure that was used for the study followed by the clustering level provided by the dataset. In cases where it is not clear which organ the data came from or if multiple organs have been used, the author should use 'body proper' (UBERON:0013702).
- **Organ_ID:** This column contains the Uberon ID for the anatomical structure described in the Organ_Level column.
- **Annotation_Label_ID:** Unique ID that is specific for each dataset.
- **Annotation_Label:** Describes the cell type that is being mapped with the original nomenclature that was used to annotate.
- **CL_Label:** The level of cell type granularity in a dataset often depends on the clustering algorithms used by bioinformaticians. As a result, datasets may include novel cell types, cell states, or unknown populations that are products of overclustering. Since these populations do not correspond to existing terms in the Cell Ontology, they should be mapped to a more general parent term. In the CL_Label field, annotators should use the parent term followed by a colon ":" and a differentiating description (i.e., the feature that makes the cell type more specific than the parent). The CL_ID should correspond to the parent CL term, and the CL_Match field should be set to skos:narrowMatch. If a required term is missing from the Cell Ontology, the Lead Crosswalk Author should consider opening an issue in the CL repository to request its addition, e.g., [request for the addition of cycling cells](#). Examples are shown in **Table 1** below.

Table 1. More specific annotation labels should be annotated to a higher level Cell Ontology (CL) term, followed by the differentia. Examples of annotation labels that do not exactly match an existing term in CL. In these cases, a higher level CL label should be used, followed by a colon and the differentia (the detail that makes the cell type more specific than the grouping term).

Annotation Label	CL Label	CL ID	CL Match
COCH+ fibroblast	fibroblast:COCH+	CL:0000057	skos:narrowMatch
Tem/Effector helper T cells	helper T cell:Tem/Effector	CL:0000912	skos:exactMatch

- **CL_ID:** Contains the unique CL ID.
- **CL_Match:** Indicates the semantic relationship between the annotated cell type and the referenced CL term. Use skos:exactMatch for equivalent concepts, and skos:narrowMatch when the annotated type is more specific than the CL term (e.g., a subtype or grouped population).

Limitations of the crosswalks

Datasets containing cell type annotation crosswalks often contain a cellular hierarchy that reflects the experimental cell clustering. Once the Lead Crosswalk Author incorporates cell types into the table, the level of the clustering is reflected (e.g., L3), but the relationships in the hierarchy are lost (e.g., there is no relationship described in the table between a 'B cell' and a 'naïve B cell').

Cell type annotation

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Datasets vary in the level of information available; the manual expert annotation procedure should be adjusted accordingly:

- No tissue information, no publication available: The annotator should assume that multiple tissues have been analyzed (use 'body proper' in Organ_Level). The annotation should use cell types that are not part of a specific anatomical structure.
- Tissue information available, no publication available: The annotator should explore CL for cell types that are specific for the anatomical structure. For example, if the Annotation_Label is 'epithelial cell', and the tissue used was a portion of the lung, the annotator should map to 'epithelial cell of lung'.
- Tissue information and publication available: The annotator should curate the publication for additional details (e.g., biomarkers such as genes or proteins that were used to *characterize* the cell type), since the cell type might be discussed in the text, but not reflected in the Annotation_Label.

Additional resources such as biomarker sets may support annotation to more granular CL terms. Annotators should reach out to tool developer teams to gain access to this data.

Special considerations for cell type annotations with examples

Choose the most granular cell type available in CL, based on the tissue location for the cell. For example, use annotation 'bronchial goblet cell' instead of lung goblet cell or more generally, 'goblet cell', see example in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Examples of annotations for more granular/organ-specific cell types. The most specific cell type should be used in the annotation, for example, if the organ level is the lung, the lung-specific cell term should be used, if available.

Organ_Level	Annotation_Label	CL_Label	CL_ID	CL_Match
Lung_v2_finetest_level ¹	Goblet (subsegmental)	bronchial goblet cell: subsegmental bronchus	CL:1000312	skos:narrowMatch
Lung_v2_finetest_level	Ionocyte	pulmonary ionocyte	CL:0017000	skos:exactMatch
Adult_Human_Skin_pkl	LC	epidermal Langerhans cell	CL:0002457	skos:exactMatch
Adult_Human_Skin_pkl	Melanocyte	Melanocyte of skin	CL:1000458	skos:exactMatch
Human_Lung_Atlas_pkl ²	Mesothelium	mesothelial cell of pleura	CL:1000491	skos:exactMatch
heart_L1	Atria-enriched endothelial cells	cardiac endothelial cell:atrial-enriched	CL:0010008	skos:narrowMatch
Human_AdultAged_Hippocampus_pkl	Astrocytes	hippocampal astrocyte	CL:0002604	skos:exactMatch

¹Note - in the first example, we included the 'subsegmental bronchus' after the semi-colon because this more specific term is not in CL and this is therefore a skos:narrowMatch.

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²Mesothelial cells in the lung are always in the pleura.

Species: for species-specific annotations, i.e., where CL has a species-specific version of a cell class, use that term. If there is a human specific term in CL, it should be used, see example in **Table 3**.

Table 3. Species-specific (human) annotations should be used when available.

Annotation_Label	CL_Label	CL_ID	CL_Match
NK_CD56bright	CD16-negative, CD56-bright natural killer cell, human	CL:0000938	skos:exactMatch
Plasmacytoid Dendritic	plasmacytoid dendritic cell, human	CL:0001058	skos:exactMatch
DC	dendritic cell, human	CL:0001056	skos:exactMatch

Annotate up if more specific terms are not available. For example, in the first row in **Table 4**, the term refers to hepatic stellate cells/myofibroblast. Connective tissue cell is a common parent for both of these terms. See examples in **Table 4**.

Table 4. Examples of higher level annotations, when more specific terms are not available.

Annotation_Label	CL_Label	CL_ID	CL_Match
HSC/mFB	connective tissue cell	CL:0002320	skos:narrowMatch
Monocyte/cDC	monocyte-derived dendritic cell	CL:0011031	skos:exactMatch
Megakaryocytes/platelets	myeloid cell	CL:0000763	skos:exactMatch

Specific annotations for NK cells versus NK T cells are described in **Table 5**.

Table 5. Annotations for NK cells vs NK T cells. Note, the CL differentiates between natural killer cells (NK cells) and mature natural killer T cells (mature NK T cells) and the preferred annotations.

Annotation_Label	CL_Label	CL_ID	CL_Match
NK cell	natural killer cell	CL:0000623	skos:exactMatch
NK T cell	mature NK T cell	CL:0000814	skos:exactMatch

CD14 Mono vs CD14+/CD16+: Since only CD14 mono (monocyte) is mentioned, we annotate this to 'CD14-positive monocyte' CL:0001054 (exactMatch) instead of the more specific term 'CD14-positive, CD16-negative classical monocyte' CL:0002057. This is because CL has the more general term, but this is not always the case, see **Table 6**.

Table 6. Annotations for CD14 cells versus CD14+/CD16+ cells. The Cell Ontology has a class for CD14 monocytes and this should be used in cases where the CD16 status is not mentioned.

Annotation_Label	CL_Label	CL_ID	CL_Match
CD14 mono or CD14+Mo	CD14-positive monocyte	CL:0001054	skos:exactMatch

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DC1 and DC2: There is an open ticket in GitHub to address conventional dendritic cells (DC1 and DC2): <https://github.com/obophenotype/cell-ontology/issues/839>. Until this ticket is addressed, DC1 and DC2 should be annotated as shown in **Table 7**.

Table 7: Annotations for DC1 or DC2 cells. Until the open GitHub ticket is addressed to differentiate between DC1 and DC2 cells, the annotations noted below should be used for these cell types.

Annotation_Label	CL_Label	CL_ID	CL_Match
DC1 (or cDC1)	CD141-positive myeloid dendritic cell	CL:0002394	skos:exactMatch
DC2 (or cDC2)	CD1c-positive myeloid dendritic cell	CL:0002399	skos:exactMatch

Terms that reference a biological process—such as “DZ cell cycle exit”—are interpreted as describing a specific cell type (e.g., dark zone B cell) in a defined functional or cell cycle state. In such cases, annotate the core cell type (e.g., germinal center B cell:dark zone, cell cycle exit) as a narrow match. An example is provided in **Table 8**.

Table 8. Annotation of a cell undergoing a biological process. In the specific example below, DZ is referring to a dark zone germinal center B cell undergoing cell cycle exit. The most specific cell type in CL is germinal center B cell and the differentia is dark zone, cell cycle exit, which should be written after the colon and is a narrow match (see **Table 1** for additional examples of differentia).

Annotation_Label	CL_Label	CL_ID	CL_Match
DZ cell cycle exit	germinal center B cell:dark zone, cell cycle exit	CL:0000844	skos:narrowMatch

In the case where there is a very vague description, annotate the high level ‘cell term’. See examples in **Table 9**.

Table 9. Annotations to CL:0000000 ‘cell’. Vague descriptions are annotated to the top level cell type “cell” (CL:0000000) and differentia is added after a colon. (See Table 1 for additional examples of differentia).

Annotation_Label	CL_Label	CL_ID	CL_Match
rare	cell:rare	CL:0000000	skos:narrowMatch
unknown cell	cell:unknown	CL:0000000	skos:narrowMatch

Some descriptions of immune cells are vague and unintuitive. Sample annotations for specific immune cells are noted in **Table 10**.

Table 10. Select immune cells. Examples of annotations needed for specific immune cell types.

Annotation_Label	CL_Label	CL_ID	CL_Match
immune	leukocyte	CL:0000738	skos:exactMatch
Lymphoid	lymphocyte	CL:0000542	skos:exactMatch

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Lymphoid DC	plasmacytoid dendritic cell (note - lymphoid DC is an exact synonym)	CL:0000784	skos:exactMatch
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Smooth muscle cells: In Cell Ontology, there is a specific term for smooth muscle cell (CL:0000192) but if this cell is present in the heart, we annotate it to vascular associated smooth muscle cell:arterial CL:0000359. Examples are provided in **Table 11**.

Table 11. Smooth muscle cells. Annotations for heart-associated smooth muscle cells should be annotated to 'vascular associated smooth muscle cell'.

Organ Level	Annotation Label	CL Label	CL ID	CL Match
heart_L1	Arterial SMC	vascular associated smooth muscle cell:arterial	CL:0000359	skos:narrowMatch
heart_L1	Basic SMC	vascular associated smooth muscle cell	CL:0000359	skos:exactMatch

Neuronal cells outside the brain are annotated as Schwann cells. Specific examples are noted in **Table 12**.

Table 12. Neuronal cells. Neuronal cells located outside of the brain are annotated as Schwann cells.

Organ Level	Annotation Label	CL Label	CL ID	CL Match
heart_L1	Neuronal cells	Schwann cell	CL:0002573	skos:narrowMatch
Kidney_L3	Schwann / Neural	Schwann cell	CL:0002573	skos:narrowMatch

Lineage cells should be annotated to the specific lineage related cell type, if available (see first row in **Table 13**). Otherwise they can be annotated to the cell type as a narrow match (see row 2 in **Table 13**).

Table 13. Annotations of lineage cells. Annotations of lineage cells should be annotated to the specific lineage-related cell type, if available or to the cell type as a narrow match.

Annotation Label	CL Label	CL ID	CL Match
B cell lineage	lymphocyte of B lineage	CL:0000945	skos:exactMatch
T cell lineage	T cell	CL:0000084	skos:narrowMatch
Multiciliated lineage	multiciliated epithelial cell	CL:0005012	skos:exactMatch

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Precursor/progenitor cells should be annotated to the higher level term if a more specific term is not available. We can consider requesting new terms to CL. Examples are shown in **Table 14**.

Table 14. Annotations of precursor/progenitor cells. Annotations should be to the higher level term if a more specific term is not available, as shown in the examples.

Annotation Label	CL Label	CL ID	CL Match
DC precursor	progenitor cell	CL:0011026	skos:narrowMatch
pDC precursor	immature CD11c-low plasmacytoid dendritic cell	CL:0000992	skos:exactMatch
Erythroid	erythroid lineage cell	CL:0000764	skos:exactMatch

“Like-cells,” such as MAIT-like, should be annotated to the primary cell type, with the ‘like’ added after the colon, see examples in **Table 15**.

Table 15. Annotations of “like-cells”. Annotations to ‘like-cells’ should be made to the primary cell type, followed by the ‘like’ after the colon.

Annotation Label	CL Label	CL ID	CL Match
MAIT-like	mature alpha-beta T cell:Mucosal-associated invariant T-like cell	CL:0000791	skos:narrowMatch
PC4_CMC-like	pericyte:cardiomyocyte-like	CL:0000669	skos:narrowMatch
CMC-like pericytes	pericyte:cardiomyocyte-like	CL:0000669	skos:narrowMatch
Fibroblast-like endothelial cells	endothelial cell:fibroblast-like	CL:0000115	skos:narrowMatch

Terms that are broad synonyms should be annotated as a narrow match. In **Table 16**, an example is shown where the label matches as a broad synonym on a CL term.

Table 16. Annotating to broad synonyms. If the term matches a broad synonym on a CL term, the CL_Match should be skos:narrowMatch.

Annotation Label	CL Label	CL ID	CL Match
Lipofibroblasts	alveolar type 1 fibroblast cell (lipofibroblast is a broad synonym)	CL:4028004	skos:narrowMatch

Tools

Multiple tools can be used to find the correct cell types in CL:

- **CL.owl file in Protégé:** Protégé is a desktop ontology editor that allows exploration of the CL ontology. It supports text-based searches, metadata inspection, and DL queries,

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making it suitable for identifying candidate CL terms manually. See

<https://protege.stanford.edu>.

- **Ontology Lookup Service (OLS):** OLS is a web-based repository for biomedical ontologies, including CL. It enables browsing, term searching, and access to ontology metadata through an intuitive user interface or via API. See <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4>.
- **LLM-based cell type mapping tool (currently under development):** A custom tool that uses large language model (LLM) text embeddings (e.g., OpenAI) and cosine similarity to compare input cell type labels to CL terms and identify the most similar matches.

References and Resources

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Glossary

anatomical structure (AS): An anatomical structure is a distinct biological entity with a 3D volume and shape, e.g., an organ, functional tissue unit, or cell.

bash: is an interactive command interpreter and programming language developed for Unix-like operating systems.

Cell Ontology (CL): an ontology designed to classify and describe cell types across different organisms. It serves as a resource for model organism and bioinformatics databases. The ontology covers a broad range of cell types in animal cells, with over 2700 cell type classes, and provides high-level cell type classes as mapping points for cell type classes in ontologies representing other species, such as the Plant Ontology or Drosophila Anatomy Ontology. Integration with other ontologies such as Uberon, GO, CHEBI, PR, and PATO enables linking cell types to anatomical structures, biological processes, and other relevant concepts.

cell type annotation crosswalks: A collection of CSV files that link cell type labels from multiple datasets to Cell Ontology (CL) or Provisional Cell Ontology IDs so they can be connected to ASCT+B tables and other digital objects that are part of the Human Reference Atlas.

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cell types: Mammalian cells are biological units with a defined function that typically have a nucleus and cytoplasm surrounded by a membrane. Each cell type may have broad common functions across organs and specialized functions or morphological or molecular features within each organ or region. Tissue is composed of different (resident and transitory) cell types that are characterized or identified via biomarkers.

cosine similarity: Measures the cosine of the angle between two vectors, with 1 indicating identical vector directions and 0 indicating no similarity.

digital object identifier (DOI): Centrally registered identifier composed of a string of numbers, letters and symbols used to uniquely identify an article or document with a permanent web address or Uniform Resource Locator (URL).

ontology: A set of subject area concepts (here, anatomical structures, cell types and biomarkers), their properties and the relationships between them. Examples: Uberon, Foundational Model of Anatomy, Cell Ontology.

skos:exactMatch: Indicates that two concepts are semantically equivalent across different vocabularies or ontologies. Used when the annotated cell type and the referenced Cell Ontology term refer to the same biological entity.

skos:narrowMatch: Indicates that the source concept is more specific than the target concept. Used when the annotated cell type represents a subtype or specific grouping not fully captured by the broader Cell Ontology term.

Uberon: Uberon is an integrated cross-species anatomy ontology covering animals and bridging multiple species-specific ontologies.

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Appendix A. Cell Type Annotation Crosswalk Template

Cell Type Annotation Crosswalk of <insert CTann DO name> annotated cells to Cell Ontology						
Author Name(s):	Semicolon delimited					
Author ORCID(s):	Semicolon delimited, same order as author list					
Reviewer(s):	Semicolon delimited					
Reviewer ORCID(s):	Semicolon delimited, same order as reviewer list					
General Publication(s):						
Data DOI:	Will be added after table is finalized and published					
Date:	Will be added for HRA release availability					
Version number:	v					
Organ_Level	Organ_ID	Annotation_Label	Annotation_Label	CL_Label	CL_ID	CL_Match